

777372 - RESOLUTE

Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

WP8 – Knowledge
integration and data
management

D8.3 Data Management Plan 3

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Document History

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V0.2	05 Nov 2018	added text / bullet points from the grant agreement (UG)
V0.3	06 Dec 2018	reworked document structure (UG)
V0.4	07 Dec 2018	added FAIR Data chapter (UG)
V0.5	09 Dec 2018	added Data Curation and Data Security (UG)
V0.6	10 Dec 2018	added Data Types (UG)
V0.7	20 Dec 2018	added Data Type for assay development (LS)
V0.8	27 Dec 2018	merged versions, added figures, added identifier schema (UG)
V0.9	02 Jan 2019	Final check, minor corrections (GE)
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V1.1	07 Dec 2020	Started draft for mid-term update (UG)
V1.2	11 Dec 2020	updated Transcriptomics data types (UG)
V1.3	12 Dec 2020	updated main text (UG)
V1.4	13 Dec 2020	updated protocols, transcriptomics, CRISPR screen, and ionomics
V1.5	14 Dec 2020	updated assays, structural models, proteomics, metabolomics,
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V2.0	31 Dec 2020	Final version reviewed and approved by all participants
V2.1	21 May 2021	Updated transcriptomics section (UG)
V2.2	24 Sep 2021	Updated transcriptomics section based on WT-OE data release
V2.3	05 Dec 2023	Started draft for end-of-project update (UG)
V2.4	06 Dec 2023	Added Table 1 summarizing data releases (UG)
V2.5	07 Dec 2023	Updated data sustainability and data preservation sections (UG)
V2.6	11 Dec 2023	Minor text changes, added ChEMBL repository for Assay data (UG)
V3.0	22 Dec 2023	Final version reviewed and approved by all participants

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Abstract

RESOLUTE is a public-private partnership with 13 partners from academia and industry with an overarching goal: To trigger an escalation in the appreciation and intensity of research on solute carriers (SLCs) worldwide and to establish SLCs as a tractable target class for medical research and development. Through the coupling of an inclusive, “open-access ethos” to the data, results, techniques and reagents with the highest-possible quality of research output, RESOLUTE expects to accelerate the pace and increase the impact of research in the field of SLCs to the global benefit of basic academic research through to applied research in SMEs and pharmaceutical companies.

Data management plays a major role in the project by providing a central data repository for collecting, curating, sharing, integrating, analysing and publishing data generated across the individual work packages and consortium members. This data management plan (DMP) describes the infrastructure, policies and life cycle for research data generated and/or processed throughout the RESOLUTE project. It is intended to be a living document and was updated throughout the project whenever significant changes occurred. The initial data management plan (Deliverable 8.1) was extended considerably for the mid-term update (Deliverable 8.2) with many more details on the individual data types. This third and final version of the data management plan builds on the previous versions, incorporating minor changes that have occurred to different data modalities over the course of the project, and in addition puts and emphasis on sustainability and outlook for the period after the project end.

Research Data

Virtually every individual task of the RESOLUTE project depends on or produces data in order to develop reagents, functionalize SLCs or set up assays. On the one hand, existing data in the public domain or with permissive licenses is collected, mined and compiled into the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Deliverable 8.4). A majority of data, on the other hand, is newly generated, processed and analysed throughout the project. This process is supported by the RESOLUTE database (Deliverable 8.5). Both resources are accessible from the RESOLUTE web portal at <https://re-solute.eu> (Deliverable 8.6; see Figure 1). For more details, please refer to *Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase* on page 27.

Most data generated in course of RESOLUTE is disseminated through the RESOLUTE web portal and also preserved in domain specific, sustainable, public repositories (see also *Data Lifecycle* on page 27 data type specific information on page 6).

Data Ownership

Data is inherently owned by the institution of its producer (see also *Consortium Agreement* paragraph 7.1.1).

Data Types

A multitude of types of data is produced in the course of the RESOLUTE project, ranging from primary omics data over reagents to analysis tools, workflows and scientific publications. The following table describes the different data types and levels, and their corresponding format, standards, primary organizing principles (POPs) and relations in detail.

▪ Protocols & Workflows

<i>Data Group</i>	Protocols & Workflows
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Description of a number of steps to generate a sample, conduct an experiment or process data.
<i>Data Origin</i>	all tasks generating samples, conducting experiments and running analyses
<i>Data Types:</i>	
Sample Preparation Protocol	
<i>Data Format</i>	free text
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experimental factors key: Experimental Factor Ontology; BioAssay Ontology; Ontology for Biomedical Investigations value: any
<i>Data Author</i>	all consortium partners
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - public repositories for protocols (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Used to prepare a sample for subsequent experimental analysis, resulting in any of the primary data types listed below.
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected protocols are submitted to one of the following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) - Bio-protocol (https://bio-protocol.org) - protocols.io (https://www.protocols.io)
Experimental Protocol	
<i>Data Format</i>	free text
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	all consortium partners

<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - public repositories for protocols (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Used to analyse a sample, resulting in any of the primary data types listed in other data types below.
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected protocols are submitted to one of the following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) - Bio-protocol (https://bio-protocol.org) - protocols.io (https://www.protocols.io)
Data Processing Workflow	
<i>Data Format</i>	free text / software code / Docker image
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM and also other partners
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internal GitLab server
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public repositories for software (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Used to process raw results, typically extracting and quantifying measurements for relevant biological entities (e.g. metabolites, proteins, ...).
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected workflows are submitted to one of the following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GitHub (https://github.com) - Docker Hub (https://hub.docker.com)
Data Analysis Workflow	
<i>Data Format</i>	free text / software code / Docker image
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM and also other partners
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internal GitLab server
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public repositories for software (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Used to analyse processed, quantitative data; typically in the context of some hypothesis, statistical test and specific visualization methods.
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB

<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected workflows are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - GitHub (https://github.com/re-solute)
Data Mining Workflow	
<i>Data Format</i>	KNIME workflows (open, documented format)
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	UniVie
<i>Data Sharing</i>	internal KNIME server
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- scientific publications - Microsoft Azure cloud - public repositories for workflows (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Used to support tractability analysis for priority list generation (Tasks 4.1 to 4.4) and also the rest of the project with general data mining (Task 8.5).
<i>Data Volume</i>	expected: 10 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected workflows are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - KNIME Hub (https://hub.knime.com)

▪ **Transcriptomics**

<i>Data Group</i>	Transcriptomics
<i>Data Group Description</i>	RNA-Seq analysis of cell lines using NGS.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 1.5 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls) Task 7.1 (knockout cell lines of priority SLCs under perturbation conditions)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
RNA measurements of cell lines using NGS	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	FASTQ (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Illumina high-throughput sequencing of isolated RNA (BI: Illumina NovaSeq; Sanofi: Illumina NextSeq 500)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- RNA isolation protocol - library preparation protocol
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument type - instrument method

<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MultiQC software - per base sequence quality (Phred scores) - per base sequence content - per sequence GC content - per base N content - sequence duplication level - adapter content - k-mer content
<i>Data Author</i>	Boehringer (T1.5), Sanofi (T7.1)
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amazon S3 buckets (Boehringer) - SFTP server (Sanofi)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for transcriptomics data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to mapping to a reference genome and quantification (see <i>Quantitative gene expression</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	currently: 2.5 TB expected: 10 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EBI's European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)
Quantitative gene expression	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Processing workflow applied to raw reads from <i>RNA measurements of cell lines using NGS</i> on page 8.
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - genes key: Ensembl gene identifier (ENSG) value: counts; TPM - transcripts key: Ensembl transcript identifier (ENST) value: counts; TPM
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - read trimming and clipping method - reference gene and transcript model used (e.g. ENSEMBL GRCh38, release 94) - software version and parameters used for read mapping and quantitation - normalization procedure
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gene body coverage (no 3' bias) - mapping rate - unique mapping rate - gene model mapping rate - replicate correlation - clustering of replicates on PCA
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database

<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - serves as input to differential expression analyses (see <i>Differential Transcript Expression Analysis</i> below) - data from Task 1.5 is published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase - data serves as QC for cell line generation (Tasks 1.1 to 1.4)
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed transcriptomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to ENA.
Differential Transcript Expression Analysis	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	read count matrices obtained in <i>Quantitative gene expression</i> on page 9
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - genes <i>key</i>: Ensembl gene identifier (ENSG) <i>value</i>: log₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value - transcripts <i>key</i>: Ensembl transcript identifier (ENST) <i>value</i>: log₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-filtering - statistical model - contrasts (WT-OE: induced vs. uninduced; KO: SLC vs renilla; KO-OE: induced vs. uninduced)
<i>Quality Control</i>	- differential expression analysis between negative controls
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Package 3 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, analysed transcriptomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to ENA.

▪ CRISPR screens

<i>Data Group</i>	CRISPR screens
<i>Data Description</i>	Pooled CRISPR viability screens using a SLC-wide sgRNA library
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.5 (Genetic interactions)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
pooled sgRNA profiling using NGS	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	BAM (community accepted, open, binary format)

<i>Data Source</i>	Illumina high-throughput sequencing
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	None
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- library preparation protocol
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument type - instrument method
<i>Quality Control</i>	- per base sequence quality (Phred scores)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for CRISPR screens (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to mapping reads to the sgRNA library (see <i>Quantitative viability in SLC-wide CRISPR screen</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	currently: none expected: 2 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - EBI's European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)
Quantitative viability in SLC-wide CRISPR screen	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Demultiplexing and mapping of reads from <i>pooled sgRNA profiling using NGS</i> on page 10 to a reference library.
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- sgRNA <i>key</i> : RESOLUTE sgRNA identifier <i>value</i> : counts
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	- mapping parameters - sgRNA library used - barcodes used
<i>Quality Control</i>	- mapping rate of barcodes - mapping rate of guides
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to genetic interaction analysis (see <i>Genetic interaction analysis</i> below).
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed CRISPR screen data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to public repositories.
Genetic interaction analysis	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)

<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	read count matrices obtained in <i>Quantitative viability in SLC-wide CRISPR screen</i> on page 11
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- pairs of genes <i>key</i> : Ensembl gene identifier (ENSG) <i>value</i> : genetic interaction score
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	- pre-filtering - normalization procedure - scoring model - network representation thresholds
<i>Quality Control</i>	- count distributions and outlier detection - clustering of replicates and time points on PCA - renilla KO cell lines should not interact
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Input to priority list generation in Task 4.2
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, analysed CRISPR screen data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to public repositories.

▪ Ionomics

<i>Data Group</i>	Ionomics
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Targeted relative and absolute quantitation of selected elemental ions using ICP-MS.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.8 (Ionomic profiling to identify SLCs using ions as (co-)substrates)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
Targeted mass-spectrometric analysis for selected ions	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	vendor specific, proprietary format
<i>Data Source</i>	ICP-MS analysis of cell lysates (3 to 4 replicates)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	none
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument method
<i>Quality Control</i>	- instrument mass offset - QC samples to check whether a run is valid - RSD (relative standard deviation) of every sample measurement is checked

<i>Data Author</i>	Vifor (International) Ltd.; CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	raw mass spectra are not shared
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	none
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Recorded mass spectra serve as input to <i>Relative quantification of elemental ions</i> below
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	none
Relative quantification of elemental ions	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	automatic signal intensity calculation based on mass spectra from <i>Targeted mass-spectrometric analysis for selected ions</i> on page 12; relative to an internal standard to control for sample loading; blank values already subtracted
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - analyte key: chemical element name (IUPAC) values: relative intensity (a.u.: cps relative to cps of internal standard); normalized intensity (relative intensity per mg/ml protein)
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sample's protein abundance (BCA) for normalization
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - calibration curve - reproducibility between replicates (CV) - clustering of replicates on PCA
<i>Data Author</i>	Vifor (International) Ltd.
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database - general-purpose, public research repositories (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to <i>Differential ionomics analyses</i> below and <i>Absolute quantification of elemental ions</i> on page 14
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	<p>Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public general-purpose research data repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) - Data Dryad (https://datadryad.org) - BioStudies (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/)
Differential ionomics analyses	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	ion abundance matrices obtained in <i>Relative quantification of elemental ions</i> above

<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- analyte <i>key</i> : chemical element name (IUPAC) <i>value</i> : log ₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	- pre-filtering - normalization procedure - statistical model - contrasts: WT-OE induced vs. uninduced; KO-OE induced vs. uninduced
<i>Quality Control</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- characterization of SLCs on ion activity - supports decision process for assay development in Work Package 3 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Differential ionomics analyses are submitted together with corresponding relative abundance data sets to public repositories.
Absolute quantification of elemental ions for selected samples	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	ion abundance matrices obtained in <i>Relative quantification of elemental ions</i> on page 13 combined with standard curves to derive absolute quantitative values
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- analyte <i>key</i> : chemical element name (IUPAC) <i>value</i> : concentration
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	standard curve parameters
<i>Quality Control</i>	quality criteria for standard curve - QC samples to check whether a run is valid - RSD (relative standard deviation) of every sample measurement is checked
<i>Data Author</i>	Vifor (International) Ltd.
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database - general-purpose, public research repositories (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- supports assay development in Work Package 3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB

<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Differential ionomics analyses are submitted together with corresponding relative abundance data sets to public repositories.
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▪ Homology models

<i>Data Group</i>	Homology models
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Modelled structures for SLCs based on experimental structures of similar sequences.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 8.5 (Data mining)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
3D structural models	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	PDB (community accepted, open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	computed; based on atomic coordinates from template structures (e.g. from PDB)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- template key: template value: PDB chain
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	- sequence alignment - modelling script / parameters
<i>Quality Control</i>	- accuracy of the template/target alignment - structure evaluation parameters and assessment scores (PROCHECK and PROQM) - enrichment calculations to assess the models' utility for virtual screening
<i>Data Author</i>	UniVie
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - public repositories for structural models (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- helps understanding the mechanism of transport (WP2, Deorphanization) - helps to predicts new compounds (WP2, Deorphanization) - useful to conduct SAR studies - input for potential docking experiments or molecular dynamics simulations
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected structural models are submitted to the following public repositories: - ModelArchive (https://modelarchive.org)

▪ Binders

<i>Data Group</i>	Binders
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<i>Data Group Description</i>	Generation of high affinity binders for selected SLC proteins.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 5.3 (binder generation) and Task 5.4 (binder validation)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
binder sequences	
<i>Data Format</i>	text (protein sequence)
<i>Data Source</i>	derived from experiments
<i>Metadata</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - type of antigen used (e.g. proteoliposomes) - binder generation platform used
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - validate binder specificity (WT vs. KO cell lines; OE vs. KO cell lines)
<i>Data Author</i>	5 different sub-contracted producers
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - Human Protein Atlas
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports assay development in Work Package 3 - helps identify SLC subcellular localization in Task 2.7 - potentially support efforts of RESOLUTE Structural Biology Alliance in reducing protein flexibility - used for <i>binder validation</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	<p>Selected binder sequences are submitted to one of the following public repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) - Human Protein Atlas (https://www.proteinatlas.org)
binder validation	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	<p>binder specificity (numerical), derived from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in-vitro (binding curve) - immuno-fluorescence (images) - western-blot (images)
<i>Data Source</i>	validation experiments based on commercially available antibodies (YCHAROS) as well as <i>binder sequences</i> above by cloning sequences into plasmid
<i>Data Author</i>	SGC; Bayer (Nuvisan); CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - used for quality control and evaluation of <i>binder sequences</i> above
<i>Data Volume</i>	expected: 100 GB

<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected binder validation data are submitted together with the corresponding binder sequence data to Zenodo or Human Protein Atlas.
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▪ **Targeted Metabolomics**

<i>Data Group</i>	Targeted Metabolomics
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Quantitative measurement of a set of selected metabolites in cell extracts.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.1 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls) Task 7.1 (knockout cell lines of priority SLCs under perturbation conditions)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
LC-MS/MS metabolomics	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	Mass Hunter raw files (vendor specific, proprietary format; potentially converted to open mzML format)
<i>Data Source</i>	HPLC-MS/MS analysis of cell extracts (Agilent 6470 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- metabolite extraction protocol
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument setup - instrument method (METAB02)
<i>Quality Control</i>	- system stability test (calibration mix in level 4 dilution) - QC sample (NIST1950) run after every 10 samples - RESOLUTE serum QC sample
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for metabolomics data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to <i>Metabolites quantitation</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	currently: 0.3 TB expected: 1 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - EBI's MetaboLights (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/)
Metabolites quantitation	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Processing workflow for peak picking and integration applied to mass spectra obtained in <i>LC-MS/MS metabolomics</i> above.

<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- metabolite <i>key</i> : ChEBI identifier <i>value</i> : intensity; concentration
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	- software version (MassHunter v10.0) and parameters used for peak identification and integration - internal standards and calibration curve (for absolute quantitation) - normalization procedure
<i>Quality Control</i>	- internal standards for retention time - replicate correlation - clustering of replicates on PCA
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- serves as input to <i>Differential Metabolite Abundance Analysis</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed metabolomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to MetaboLights.
Differential Metabolite Abundance Analysis	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	numerical matrices obtained in <i>Metabolites quantitation</i> on page 17
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- metabolite <i>key</i> : ChEBI identifier <i>values</i> : log ₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	- pre-filtering - statistical model - contrasts (WT-OE: induced vs. uninduced; KO-OE: induced vs. uninduced)
<i>Quality Control</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Package 3 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, analysed metabolomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to MetaboLights.

▪ **Untargeted Metabolomics**

<i>Data Group</i>	Untargeted Metabolomics
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Measurement of intra- and extracellular compounds.
<i>Data Origin</i>	Tasks 2.2 and Task 2.3 (parental cell lines, knockout and overexpression cell lines, required controls)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
LC-MS/MS metabolomics	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	Thermo .raw files (vendor specific, proprietary format; potentially converted to open mzML format)
<i>Data Source</i>	LC-MS/MS analysis of intracellular and extracellular extracts (Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- metabolite extraction protocol
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument setup - instrument calibration & tuning - instrument method
<i>Quality Control</i>	- QC and long term reference (LTR) QA samples to assess system stability - RESOLUTE serum QC sample
<i>Data Author</i>	University of Liverpool; Pfizer; CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- SFTP server (CeMM) - Microsoft Azure Cloud
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for metabolomics data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to <i>Metabolites identification and quantitation</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	expected: 5 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - EBI's MetaboLights (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/)
Metabolites identification and quantitation	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Processing workflow for peak picking, identification and integration applied to mass spectra obtained in <i>LC-MS/MS metabolomics</i> above.
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- compound <i>key:</i> m/z ratio; retention time <i>values:</i> intensity; matching ChEBI identifiers

<i>Metadata Processing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - software version and parameters used for peak identification and integration - retention time alignment - normalization procedure
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - replicate correlation - clustering of replicates on PCA - clustering of replicate QA and QC samples on PCA - blank measurements
<i>Data Author</i>	University of Liverpool; Pfizer
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- serves as input to <i>Differential Metabolite Abundance Analysis</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed metabolomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to MetaboLights.
Differential Metabolite Abundance Analysis	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	numerical matrices obtained in <i>Metabolites identification and quantitation</i> on page 19
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - compounds <li style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>key</i>: ChEBI identifiers <li style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>values</i>: log₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-filtering - statistical model - contrasts (WT-OE: induced vs. uninduced; KO-OE: induced vs. uninduced)
<i>Quality Control</i>	none
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Package 3 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.2
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, analysed metabolomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to MetaboLights.

▪ **Imaging**

<i>Data Group</i>	Imaging
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Microscopy-based high-content imaging
<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.7 (overexpression cell lines, required controls)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
Microscopy Images	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	TIFF (community accepted, open, binary format)
<i>Data Source</i>	confocal microscope
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- staining protocol
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument type - instrument method
<i>Metadata</i>	- well - field - z-stack - channel
<i>Quality Control</i>	
<i>Data Author</i>	Novartis
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- SFTP server (Novartis) - Microsoft Azure Cloud
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for imaging data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to <i>Subcellular signal quantitation</i> below.
<i>Data Volume</i>	currently: 15 TB expected: 30 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - Image Data Resource (https://idr.openmicroscopy.org) - BioImage Archive (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/) - BioStudies (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/)
Subcellular signal quantitation	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Processing workflow applied to <i>Microscopy Images</i> above in order to identify cells (segmentation) and quantify and colocalize signal for subcellular compartments.

<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - segmented cell - probe <i>keys:</i> probe name; excitation wavelength <i>value:</i> pixel intensity; colocalization coefficient
<i>Metadata Processing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - normalization method - software and parameters for image segmentation, quantification and colocalization
<i>Quality Control</i>	
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - serves as input to <i>Subcellular Localization</i> below - data serves as QC for cell line generation (Tasks 1.1 to 1.4)
<i>Data Volume</i>	expected: 10 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed imaging data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to public repositories (see above).
Subcellular Localization	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Based on <i>Subcellular signal quantitation</i> on page 21.
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - subcellular localization <i>key:</i> gene ontology (GO) <i>value:</i> probability
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-filtering - statistical model
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - known, well reported subcellular localization of selected SLCs - subcellular localization using high-affinity binders (WP5)
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports decision process for assay development in Work Package 3 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, analysed subcellular localization data are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to public repositories (see above).

▪ **Interaction Proteomics**

<i>Data Group</i>	Interaction Proteomics
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Measurement and analysis of interactome of targeted SLC proteins.

<i>Data Origin</i>	Task 2.6 (AP-MS) Task 7.2 (BioID, AP-MS)
<i>Data Types:</i>	
LC-MS/MS proteomics analysis of interactomes	
<i>Data Level</i>	primary (raw)
<i>Data Format</i>	raw (vendor specific, proprietary format; can be converted to open mzML format)
<i>Data Source</i>	LC-MS/MS (Thermo Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	none
<i>Metadata Sample Preparation</i>	- protein enrichment protocol (e.g. subcellular enrichment for mitochondrial baits)
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	- instrument type - instrument method
<i>Quality Control</i>	- custom Skyline workflows - spectral identification rate - total ion current - chromatogram / ion map
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- Microsoft Azure Cloud - public repositories for proteomics data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	Serves as input to <i>Peptide and Protein Identification and Quantitation</i> below.
<i>Data Volume</i>	currently: 0.8 TB expected: 5.0 TB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected data sets are submitted to one of the following public repositories: - ProteomeXchange (http://www.proteomexchange.org)
Peptide and Protein Identification and Quantitation	
<i>Data Level</i>	derived (processed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	Mapping mass spectra to peptides from a reference database and quantifying peak intensity with primary data from <i>LC-MS/MS proteomics analysis of interactomes</i> above.
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	- peptides <i>key</i> : sequence <i>value</i> : intensity; spectral counts - proteins <i>key</i> : neXtProt protein identifier (NX) <i>value</i> : intensity; spectral counts

<i>Metadata Processing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reference protein database - software version and parameters used for peak picking and quantitation - software version and parameters used for peptide-spectrum-matching - normalization procedure
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - amount of contamination - success rate of peptide-spectrum-matching - score distributions in a target-decoy approach - replicate correlation - clustering of replicates on PCA
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	- internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	- public RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	- data serves as input to <i>Protein Interaction Network</i> below
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected, processed proteomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to ProteomeXchange.
Protein Interaction Network	
<i>Data Level</i>	interpreted (analysed)
<i>Data Format</i>	TSV tab-separated values (open, human readable format)
<i>Data Source</i>	modelling of significant binding partners based on <i>Peptide and Protein Identification and Quantitation</i> on page 23
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - protein key: neXtProt (NX) value: log₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value - gene key: Ensemble gene identifier (ENSG) value: log₂ fold-change; adjusted p-value
<i>Metadata Analysis</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-filtering - data normalization procedure - statistical model - contrasts (SLC vs. negative GFP control; SLC vs. SLC) - network representation thresholds
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - clustering of replicates on PCA - positive control of known interaction partners - overlap with publicly reported interactions (BioGRID, BioPlex) - integration of subcellular localization data - integration of CRAPome reference data sets
<i>Data Author</i>	CeMM
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database (Dashboards)

<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public RESOLUTE database (Dashboards) - scientific publications - public repositories for protein interaction data (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports decision process on cell line selection for assay development in Work Packages 3 and 6 - input to priority list generation in Task 4.2 - input to integrative analysis in Task 7.3
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	<p>Selected, analysed interaction proteomics data sets are submitted together with corresponding primary data sets to ProteomeXchange and to one of the following public protein interaction repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BioGRID (https://thebiogrid.org) - STRING (https://string-db.org) - IntAct (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact)

▪ Assays

<i>Data Group</i>	Assays
<i>Data Group Description</i>	Development of robust assays to quantify the transport function of an individual SLC or a group of SLCs (substrate uptake assays, functional assays and binding assays).
<i>Data Origin</i>	all tasks in WP3 and WP6
<i>Data Types:</i>	
Transport Assay Method	
<i>Data Description</i>	Protocol or SOP with detailed description of the assay and its relevant primary or derived readouts (e.g. kinetics or end-point values; substrates/activators dose/response curves).
<i>Data Format</i>	free text; Microsoft Word document; PDF document; Microsoft PowerPoint slides
<i>Data Source</i>	authored
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - readouts key: BioAssay Ontology (BAO); Ontology for Biomedical Investigations; PubChem BioAssay Classification values: SQL data type; Units of measurement ontology (UO)
<i>Metadata</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assay Type / Classification (PubChem BioAssay Classification) - MIACA (Minimum Information About a Cellular Assay)
<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data robustness (e.g. RZ' factor) - reproducibility: inter-experiments and over time - performance confirmed by appropriate reference substrates / inhibitors - negative controls
<i>Data Author</i>	all WP3 and WP6 partners
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database

<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - public repositories for bio-assays (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - used to test tool compounds in Assay Characterization with tested tool compounds below - Input to priority list generation in WP4 tasks - Input from WP2: SLCs potential substrates for orphan SLCs - Input from WP3: most suitable technology to be used to set a functional assay - Input from WP4: priority target list to work on - Input from WP5: available expressed SLC proteins, for cell-free assay set up
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	<p>Selected assays are submitted to at least one of the following public repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PubChem BioAssay (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pcassay) - ChEMBL (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/) - Bio-protocol (https://bio-protocol.org)
Assay Characterization with tested tool compounds	
<i>Data Description</i>	Direct or indirect SLC functionality detection, by testing selected tool compounds.
<i>Data Format</i>	tabular; different readout formats (numbers, text, images)
<i>Data Source</i>	Application of <i>Transport Assay</i> on page 25 to selected tool compounds on KO and OE cell lines; various readout instruments (e.g. spectrophotometer, high content imaging)
<i>Primary Organizing Principles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tool compound <p>key: ChEBI identifier; InChI string</p> <p>value: assay readout</p>
<i>Metadata Experiment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - instrument
<i>Data Author</i>	all WP3 and WP6 partners
<i>Data Sharing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microsoft SharePoint - internal RESOLUTE database
<i>Data Dissemination</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific publications - public RESOLUTE database - IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY - public repositories for bio-assays (see <i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i> below)
<i>Data Relation & Utility</i>	
<i>Data Volume</i>	< 1 GB
<i>Data Sustainability & Preservation</i>	Selected assay readouts for tool compounds are submitted together with corresponding assay protocols to public bio-assay resources.

Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase

While data physically resides on the CeMM storage server and the Microsoft Azure Cloud (see *Secure Storage* on page 31), the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase represent the central points of data and knowledge management, data curation and data access throughout the RESOLUTE project.

The RESOLUTE database (Deliverable 8.5) provides an interface to *primary*, *derived* and *interpreted* data as well as corresponding *metadata*. Moreover, it is not limited to data, but is also used to identify and manage material (e.g. reagents, biological samples). Thus, it enables linking data to its origin and allows efficient implementation of data lineage and data provenance tracking. The RESOLUTE database had a restricted area, accessible to the participants only, and a public area, where published data sets are made openly accessible. The restricted area will fade out by the end of the project, as all the data sets have been publicly released.

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Deliverable 8.4) comprises mainly *reference* data, i.e. data compiled from external databases and resources. It is a comprehensive and accurate resource of integrated state-of-the-art knowledge on the various SLC families. Over the course of the project, it was expanded by selected *interpreted* data sets, i.e. analysis results from data produced in RESOLUTE, in the form of user friendly and interactive dashboards. The RESOLUTE knowledgebase is entirely open accessible.

In summary, the RESOLUTE database is experiment and data set centric, while the RESOLUTE knowledgebase focuses on biological entities. Both tools link to each other wherever appropriate.

Data Lifecycle

The generation of data takes place at the sites of participants and initially is stored locally. After passing a local quality control and an appraisal of relevance, data is uploaded to the RESOLUTE database. This submission process requires annotation of metadata. Data in the RESOLUTE database is automatically available to all participants (see *Data Sharing* on page 28). To be publicly accessible, data has to go through a data dissemination procedure (see *Data Dissemination* on page 29). Please note that when publishing the results of e.g. a differential expression analysis, the data lifecycle runs independently three times, once for the primary (raw) data, once for the derived (processed) data and once for the interpreted (analysed) data. Selected interpreted data is also published in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase.

The final “data appreciation step”, the leftmost column in the central panel of Figure 2, was planned to decide on public release of any remaining data sets. This was however not required, as all the data sets generated in the project have been publicly released through the two other possible defined ways of data publication (middle and right column).

Data Identifiers

We developed a RESOLUTE identifier schema following recently published recommendations for the field of life sciences¹. The identifiers have to be short and robust, as they will not only be used for data but also for reagents and therefore have to be written/read to/from test tubes regularly.

A RESOLUTE identifier starts with two letters, specifying the type of entity (e.g. CE for cell line). The main part consists of four alphanumeric characters specifying the actual entity. In the end, an optional checksum character adds redundancy and allows spotting typos. The main part encodes an incremental number, using the digits 0-9 and the letters A-Z with the exception of D, I, J, L, O, Q, U and Y because of their similarity to other digits or letters. This results in an alphabet of 28 symbols and thus a total of up to 614,656 words using four characters. The checksum character is taken from an extended alphabet (including Q, U and Y) and is calculated as modulo 31 (i.e. the next prime number). The identifier is not case sensitive.

This RESOLUTE identifier schema applies to most entries of the RESOLUTE database, and is therefore not limited to data, but also used to identify and manage material (e.g. reagents, biological samples) and events (e.g. experiments).

Data Sharing

All data generated or compiled is openly shared among all participants (see *Consortium Agreement* paragraph 8.1.2). Data is shared either via RESOLUTE’s Microsoft SharePoint (for documents, reports, etc.), via the RESOLUTE database (for derived and interpreted data) or via RESOLUTE’s Microsoft Azure Cloud (typically for primary data).

For sharing data with the scientific community, please refer to *Data Dissemination* on page 29.

Data Quality and Annotation

As well-structured and high-quality data is essential to higher-level analyses and data reuse, we implement multiple layers of data documentation, annotation and quality control.

When uploading data to the RESOLUTE database, a submission form requires the author to provide annotation and metadata, including consistent linkage to existing data. Once in the database, data can be reviewed and curated by all participants. While standardized data annotation is required (see also *Making data findable* on page 30).

As we expect RESOLUTE reagents and data to lay the foundation of future SLC research, highest possible quality standards have to be met. We implement quality control on three levels: A first quality control step happens at the site of data generation, and specification of corresponding quality control metrics (see *Data Types* on page 6) is required when submitting to the RESOLUTE database. In a second step of quality control, a *data release proposal* with a focus on data annotation and quality control has to be prepared before the public release of a data set. In case of a scientific publication in a journal, the peer-review process forms the third layer of quality control and assessment of data annotation. To ensure a peer-review step also for data releases without scientific publication, we implement *data annotation and release workshops* (see *Data Dissemination* on page 29).

¹ McMurry JA, et al. Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. PLoS Biol. 2017 Jun 29;15(6):e2001414. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414.

Data Dissemination

All relevant data, i.e. data generated or collected by the RESOLUTE project that passed certain quality control and data appraisal procedures, should be rapidly published under open access. Publication procedure follows one of three different routes (please also refer to the three columns in the central panel 'RESOLUTE database' in Figure 2):

- 1) **data release:** Any participant can propose data for public release by submitting a written *data release proposal* to the Work Package 8 team, specifying the following details:
 - an abstract on the data,
 - the motivation for publication,
 - the data identifiers,
 - the annotation status,
 - the standards compliance,
 - assessment of quality control,
 - license to use for publication.

Work Package 8 team collects these proposals for further discussion in *data annotation and release workshops*, taking place regularly at consortium meetings or also as tele conferences in between. Participation at the workshop is voluntary, and all participants receive the collected data release proposals two weeks before the workshop. At the workshop, the proposals are discussed in detail with the aim of curating data, extending and refining annotation and strengthening quality control, but there will be no immediate decision taken on publication. Within a week after the workshop, Work Package 8 team together with the proposal's authors send out a refined version of the data release proposal to the *publication and dissemination officers* of all consortium partners. In case there are no objections within a 30 days review period, the data is published and openly accessible in the RESOLUTE database and subsequently submitted to data-type specific, public repositories. Minor objections can be directly resolved with the objecting participant, while major objections require an adaption of the proposal, effectively restarting the review period.

- 2) **supporting a scientific publication:** Data might also be disseminated as integral part or supplemental material to a scientific, peer-reviewed publication. For this route, the same *data release proposal* as described above has to be submitted to Work Package 8 team, but a data annotation and release workshop is not required. All scientific publications follow the *gold or hybrid* open access policy by submitting the manuscripts to open access journals or by paying for this option in the subscription-only journals. For more details on dissemination in the form of scientific publications, please refer to the *Dissemination and Exploitation Plan* (Deliverable 9.2).
- 3) **end of project:** At the end of the project (i.e. December 2023) we intended to release and make openly accessible a majority of all data within the RESOLUTE database that was not published before. A final *data annotation and release workshop* should help to select data sets for publication. However, as all the data sets generated in the project have been published via the two other routes described above, this final workshop was not required and did not take place.

Throughout the project, we had a total of 14 individual data releases, each releasing a number of different data sets. The total data volume adds up to 46 TB of SLC specific data sets available to the scientific community as a result of the RESOLUTE project. A list of all the successful data releases can be found in Table 1 under *Data Preservation* on page 33.

FAIR Data

Participants of the RESOLUTE consortium acknowledge that living a culture of openness for this project will benefit the whole community of solute carrier research. By ensuring that all generated research data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase will efficiently lead to discovery, integration and innovation.

These efforts were significantly supported by a close collaboration with the IMI FAIRplus consortium (<https://fairplus-project.eu>). After being invited to their kick-off meeting early 2019, RESOLUTE has been selected as a pilot data set for collaborative FAIRification. The efforts were focused on RESOLUTE's initial transcriptomics and proteomics data sets, helping to bring the data to a well documented and annotated state for submission to public repositories. The biggest benefit of this collaboration was a sensibilization for the different aspects of FAIR data, which helped to properly prepare and handle all subsequently generated data sets in our project.

Making data findable

To make something findable, a synthesis of identifiability, locatability, actionability and discoverability is required. All data in the RESOLUTE database are *identifiable* by their automatically assigned, unique and persistent identifier (see *Data Identifiers* on page 28). The data is *locatable and actionable* by a direct mapping of the identifier to an URI (e.g. <https://re-solute.eu/CL0001>) as well as a corresponding CURIE (compact URI, e.g. RES:CL0001), which was registered at the resolving system of identifiers.org². The RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase allows published data to be *discoverable* in a manual way via the user-friendly web interface, and in an automated way by implementing the Bioschemas³ specification.

In addition, data is annotated with an abstract and keywords (enabling free text search), a set of generic metadata (i.e. the data author, a link to the experiment and sample, timestamps, etc.) and a set of specific metadata (see *Data Types* on page 6). By building on established metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core⁴, ISA⁵, MIBBI⁶, etc.) and controlled vocabularies and ontologies (e.g. ChEBI, MONDO, EFO), we increase the findability and interoperability of the data. Furthermore, we also encourage participants to use Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers (ORCID) for referencing their contribution to published datasets.

To further increase exposure and findability, we will register the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase at FAIRsharing⁷, a registry for research standards and databases, and re3data⁸, a registry for research data repositories.

Making data openly accessible

All data generated or collected by the RESOLUTE project undergoes certain quality control and data appraisal procedures. Data of sufficient quality and relevance is stored and shared in the RESOLUTE database and is released to be openly accessible. *Data Dissemination* on page 29 details the different routes and timelines of data publication.

Data is available at the RESOLUTE web portal (<https://re-solute.eu>; Deliverable 8.6), which forms the entry point to the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase. It provides open access to published scientific papers, reports and research data without the need for authentication or special software (apart from a standards-compliant modern web browser). In addition, corresponding metadata and licensing information is provided.

We also provide advanced tools for optimal data exploitation, i.e. a web based query system featuring interactive dashboards and reports, as well as APIs and workflow support (e.g. KNIME⁹ nodes) for automated database access and data mining (Deliverable 8.7).

Making data interoperable

Coherent use of non-proprietary, standardized data and metadata formats, aiming at maximum compliance with open source software applications, ensures interoperability of RESOLUTE data. To enable inter-disciplinary

² Wimalaratne SM, et al. Uniform resolution of compact identifiers for biomedical data. *Sci Data*. 2018 May 8;5:180029. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2018.29.

³ <http://bioschemas.org>

⁴ Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (<http://dublincore.org>)

⁵ Investigation/Study/Assay framework (<http://isa-tools.org>)

⁶ Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations (<https://fairsharing.org/collection/MIBBI>)

⁷ <https://fairsharing.org>

⁸ <https://www.re3data.org>

⁹ The Konstanz Information Miner (<https://www.knime.com>)

interoperability, relevant existing resources are referenced and metadata standards established across research domains are used (see also *Making data findable* on page 30). A special focus was put on employing ontologies wherever possible.

Increasing data re-use

We support data re-usability by a rapid data generation to publication timeline, based on our streamlined data release process (see *Data Dissemination* on page 29). Upon publication, data is openly accessible (see *Making data openly accessible* on page 30) and re-usable for third parties by a permissive open access standard license, provided either by the Creative Commons¹⁰ (typically CC-BY-4.0) or by the Open Data Commons¹¹ project. Data re-usability is also ensured by employment of strict data quality assurance processes (see *Data Quality and Annotation* on page 28).

Algorithms or analysis software tools developed in the course of the project that might be needed to re-use data and re-produce results are published alongside the data.

Data Security

While there is no highly sensitive data (like e.g. patient data) in the RESOLUTE project and all data sets are – after their public release – open access, data security is still a necessary and important issue. The following paragraphs list actual implementation and infrastructure details ensuring secure data storage, access and transfer.

Secure Storage

Documents like SOPs, protocols, reports, or meeting minutes, are collaboratively written and stored in a Microsoft SharePoint environment via a cloud-hosted service (Microsoft Office 365).

Data (primary, derived and interpreted data) are stored at local IT infrastructure of CeMM and also in the Microsoft Azure Cloud environment (Azure Blob Containers) which fulfils the rules of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Both resources are managed by the CeMM IT department. Via including Microsoft Azure Cloud storage for primary (raw) data, the full scale of estimated required storage volume for RESOLUTE (see *Data Stewardship* on page 33) is available.

To minimize the risk of data loss, a local backup strategy as well as a cloud backup strategy is in place. The local backup runs incrementally and writes to magnetic tapes (IBM Backup system). Data in the Microsoft Azure Cloud is deposited in zone-redundant storage, i.e. replicated to three separate physical locations with independent power, cooling, and networking. To rule out data manipulation or corruption we employ MD5 checksums.

Access to the CeMM storage server is strictly restricted and available only from within the CeMM intranet, while access to the Microsoft Azure Cloud storage is controlled via a carefully maintained user list at an Azure Active Directory, allowing participants to submit or review internal data. On the other hand, shared access signatures (SAS) that are created on-demand provide a secure access for public users to view and download published data.

Secure Access

Participants of the RESOLUTE consortium have access to all the documents and information in SharePoint via a personalized RESOLUTE account, managed by a Microsoft Azure Active Directory service. Implementing an OAuth2 workflow, the same RESOLUTE account is used to securely access data and information in the internal

¹⁰ <https://creativecommons.org>

¹¹ <https://opendatacommons.org>

sections of the RESOLUTE database and the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (see *Data Curation: the RESOLUTE Data- and Knowledgebase* on page 27).

Authenticated as well as unauthenticated (i.e. public) access to data and information in the RESOLUTE web portal, the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, and the RESOLUTE database is protected by implementation of transport layer security using the secure communication protocol (HTTPS) and on-demand generation of SAS codes to Microsoft Azure Storage blobs.

Secure Transfer

Data is produced by individual participants locally, but managed centrally at the CeMM. Therefore, fast and secure data transfer is required. To allow remote access to data sets and transfer via the internet to the CeMM, we employ three strategies:

1. As initial solution, we used the Microsoft SharePoint environment, which provides an easy-to-use interface for data down- and upload. However, transfer of large files or transfer of a bulk of files turned out to be cumbersome, and data at the SharePoint has to be moved manually from or to the CeMM storage server.
2. As temporary solution, we set up a SFTP server with one dedicated user account per participant, allowing for easy programmatic transfer of many and/or large files. Again, data at the SFTP server has to be moved manually from or to the CeMM storage server on demand.
3. The Microsoft Azure Cloud is securely accessible from every participant and data transfer can be automated programmatically. Also direct download links can be generated to be used in the RESOLUTE web portal, the RESOLUTE database or the RESOLUTE knowledgebase.

Data Stewardship

CeMM is hosting the storage server and web server infrastructure. We estimated production of a total data volume of up to 300 TB throughout the project, corresponding to a data production rate of 5 TB per month. Required resources for storage and backup are provided by CeMM (see *Secure Storage* on page 31) and are budgeted with a total of 200,000 EUR.

CeMM (in particular Ulrich Goldmann) is also responsible for data management, with strong support from UniVie (in particular Gerhard Ecker). At least one representative per participant takes part in the monthly tele conferences on RESOLUTE data management (Work Package 8).

Two individuals per participant are responsible for data dissemination as *dissemination officers*. In addition, all participants are encouraged to engage in the regular *data annotation and release workshops* (see *Data Dissemination* on page 29).

Data Sustainability

Published data is not only available via the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase, but is also submitted to technology-specific or domain-specific, community-accepted repositories wherever possible (e.g. EBI's European Nucleotide Archive for next-generation sequencing data, ProteomeXchange for interaction proteomics data, or MetaboLights for metabolomics data). For data-type specific sustainability implementations please refer to *Data Types* on page 6.

Data structure, data formats, metadata formats and also code base are built on standards defined by major public initiatives, such as the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) or HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative, ensuring compatibility and sustainability.

Data Preservation

By the end of the project (end of December 2023), all generated data sets that passed the defined quality controls have been formally released to the public, either by an accompanying peer-reviewed scientific publication or by a data release, which was preceded by a Data Annotation and Release Workshop (see *Data Dissemination* on page 29).

The data sets are available from the RESOLUTE web portal, which will be continued to be maintained by CeMM for (at least) 5 more years after the end of the project, i.e. end of 2028. In addition, and also for long-term preservation, the data sets are submitted domain specific, certified public data repositories. More details on data preservation are listed for each data type individually, starting on page 6, and are also summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of all RESOLUTE data releases throughout the project. Data sets are available via the RESOLUTE web portal and will be uploaded to the selected primary public repositories within months after the end of the project.

Release Date	Data Release Short Title	Data Sets	Data Volume	Selected Public Repository
27/11/2018	Transcriptome of parental cell lines	3	146 GB	European Nucleotide Archive
08/06/2019	Proteome of parental cell lines	2	675 GB	ProteomeXchange
15/11/2019	Metabolome of parental cell lines	2	<1 GB	MetaboLights
05/03/2021	Characterization of antibodies	1	<1 GB	Zenodo
02/11/2021	Transcriptomics of overexpression cell lines	3	3.5 TB	European Nucleotide Archive
	Immunofluorescence imaging of overexpression cell lines	2	22.0 TB	BiImage Archive
14/11/2022	Metabolomics of overexpression cell lines	3	200 GB	MetaboLights
	Transcriptomics of knockout cell lines	3	2.8 TB	European Nucleotide Archive
	Transcriptomics of knockout-overexpression cell lines	3	4.0 TB	European Nucleotide Archive
	Functional assays	1	<1 GB	PubChem BioAssay, ChEMBL
27/08/2023	Interaction proteomics of overexpression cell lines	3	3.3 TB	ProteomeXchange
	Ionomics of overexpression cell lines	3	<1 GB	Zenodo
	Genetic interaction screens	3	0.7 TB	European Nucleotide Archive
28/11/2023	Untargeted metabolomics of overexpression cell lines	3	9.0 TB	MetaboLights
<i>total:</i>		35	46 TB	

Ethical and Legal Considerations

There is no personal data generated in the RESOLUTE project. However, data is generated on human cell lines. For details please refer to the ethics report (Deliverables 10.1 and 10.2).

External data which might be collected and re-used (e.g. for the RESOLUTE knowledgebase) is scrutinized for ethical or legal compliance beforehand.

Appendix

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AP-MS	Affinity purification mass spectrometry
CURIE	Compact Uniform Resource Identifier
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DMP	Data Management Plan

FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HTTPS	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
ID	Identifier
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry
MD5	Message Digest algorithm; used for calculating file checksums
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
OAuth2	Open Authorization 2.0
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
PCA	Principal component analysis
POP	Primary organizing principle
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship
RESOLUTE	Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers
RNA-Seq	RNA (ribonucleic acid) sequencing
SAR	Structure–Activity Relationship
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SLC	Solute Carrier
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Consortium Members

short name	full name
CeMM	CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences
UoX	University of Oxford
UoL	University of Liverpool
AXXAM	Axxam SpA
ULei	Universiteit Leiden
MPIMR	Max-Planck Institut für medizinische Forschung
UniVie	Universität Wien
Pfizer	Pfizer Ltd.
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG
Boehringer	Boehringer Ingelheim
Vifor	Vifor International Ltd.
Sanofi	Sanofi Aventis Recherche et Développement
Bayer	Bayer AG